

No definite reaction mechanism could be established for the formation of IV and V. However, it is almost clear that the ratio of IV and V formed is dependant upon the concentration of rectified spirit. In presence of higher concentration of rectified spirit, more of IV is formed while in lower concentration of rectified spirit, V is the major product.

Experimental

The required N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) has been prepared as usual⁴.

Intramolecular cyclisation of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) in presence of anhydrous aluminium trichloride; Formation of 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II):

Anhydrous aluminium trichloride (16 g) is gradually added to an ice cold solution of I in dry diethyl ether (0.1 M; 21 g in 75 ml), maintaining the temperature at -5° . After complete addition, the reaction mixture is allowed to stand for 30 min below 10° and then refluxed for 3 hr. It is then cooled and crushed ice (~ 100 g) is gradually added to decompose the probable aluminium trichloride complex. The resultant oily mass separated at the bottom is repeatedly extracted with diethyl ether. The ethereal solution on fractional distillation gives a fraction collected at $245-248^{\circ}$ in the form of a viscous oily liquid (Found: N, 8.48; S, 18.02. C_7H_4NSCl requires N, 8.26; S, 18.88%). It is identified as 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II) on the basis of its interaction with phenyl thiocarbamide in acetone medium, when 1-(phenylformamidino)-1-phenyl thiocarbamide hydrochloride (III), m.p. 158° is obtained (Found: N, 18.31; S, 9.88. $C_{14}H_{18}N_4S_2Cl$ requires N, 18.23; S, 10.42%). The latter also gives picrate, m.p. 142° . Both these products are identified on the basis of m.m.p. with authentic samples¹.

Intermolecular condensation of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I): Formation of 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) and 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V):

(a) *Reaction in aqueous ethanol:* N-Phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) (0.1 M; 21 g) is cooled to 0° and chilled aqueous ethanol (25 ml) is added. An extremely vigorous and exothermic reaction is observed and almost immediately a pale yellow solid separates out. It is filtered, washed with a little ethanol and crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 118° (Found: N, 9.88; S, 21.92. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O$ requires N, 9.79; S, 22.39%). It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample².

(b) *Reaction in a mixture of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 1, v/v):* To N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (21 g) is gradually added a mixture of chloroform aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, v/v; 50 ml) at 0° . A vigorous exothermic reaction, accompanied by evolution of hydrogen chloride

is observed and almost immediately a pale yellow solid separates out. It is filtered, washed with a little aqueous ethanol and crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 118° (Found: N, 10.05; S, 22.55. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O$ requires N, 9.79; S, 22.39%). It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample².

(c) *Reaction in a mixture of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 2, v/v):* To an ice cold N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (21 g) is added a chilled mixture (75 ml) of chloroform-aqueous ethanol (2 : 1, v/v) when a vigorous reaction is noticed and a pale yellow solid separates out. It is filtered, washed with a little aqueous ethanol and crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 118° . It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) as usual.

The filtrate, on addition of petroleum ether, affords a semisolid mass which on trituration several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol is converted into a pale yellow solid, crystallized from glacial acetic acid/benzene/chlorobenzene, m.p. 245° (Found: N, 9.82; S, 22.45. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O$ requires N, 9.79; S, 22.39%). It is identified as 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample³.

(d) *Reaction in a mixture of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 3, v/v):* To N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (21 g) is added a mixture (100 ml) of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 3, v/v) at 0° and the reaction mixture is allowed to stand below 10° for about 30 min. A very mild reaction is noticed. The reaction mixture is then allowed to stand for 3 hr at room temperature and treated with excess petroleum ether when a semisolid mass is obtained. This, on trituration several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol, affords a pale yellow solid crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 245° . This is identified as 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample³.

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Studies on 2-pyrazolin-5-one Derivatives

(Miss) P. MITRA, A. NAYAK and A. S. MITTRA
Mayurbhanj Chemical Laboratory, Ravenshaw College,
Cuttack-753 008

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In our earlier communications, we reported that 5-pyrazolone¹⁻⁴ and its derivatives, 4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one⁵ and 2-pyrazolin-5-thione⁶, were

associated with significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Fungicidal property^{8,9} has been noted in 2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-thiazolidone and 2-pyrazolin-5-thione. It was therefore considered worthwhile to synthesise a new heterocyclic compound containing both the fungicidally active moieties, pyrazolone and thiazolidone.

4-Acetyl-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one condensed at the active methyl site of 2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-thiazolidone in ethanol to afford the compound [2-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one-4-yl)-2-(2'-mercapto-3'-aryl-4'-thiazolidone-5'-ylidene)-ethane]. The structure of the compound was established from analytical data and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compound indicate the characteristic band at 1740 cm⁻¹ for ring (>C=O), weak band at 2990 cm⁻¹ for heterocyclic -CH stretching vibration, band at 1490 cm⁻¹ for -CH₂ bonding vibration, and at 1590, 1050, 750 cm⁻¹ attributed to -C=N, -C=S, >C-S-C< stretching vibrations, respectively.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione condensed at the 5 position with phenacyl bromide in presence of ethanol and fused sodium acetate to yield 5-ether product of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione and phenacyl bromide. It does not dissolve in 10% aq. alkali and does not give any colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

The ir data indicate the absence of enolic band. Band at 1680 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of characteristic exocyclic carbonyl group absorption, aromatic nucleus at 1370 cm⁻¹ and hydrogen atoms of mono-substituted aromatic nucleus at 760 and 740 cm⁻¹. From nmr data in CDCl₃, it has been noted that peaks at δ2.2 comes as singlet for 3H of one methyl group, δ3.9 indicates a singlet for 2H, δ6.15 comes as singlet of 1H at C₄ position. Also, a multiplet in between δ7.4-δ7.9 indicates the presence of phenyl group. The molecular weight of this compound has been determined from the mass spectra and found to be 308 (M⁺). Peaks at 308, 203, 188, 173, 103, 77, 51 m/e are obtained.

The compounds thus prepared were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae* by the standard method⁶ of spore germination tests at various concentrations. It is found that only one compound (Sl. No. 9, Table 1) is active against both the pathogens. It was of further interest to note that 5 other compounds (Sl. No. 1, 5, 6, 7, 10, Table 1) were active at 1000 ppm. The compound No. 1 in Table 2 is found to be more active than the O-ether product earlier reported by Das and Mitra⁹.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Infrared spectrophotometer.

Sl. No.	R ₁	m.p. °C	%S Found (Calcd.)	% inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
				<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	167	15.65 (15.72)	62.4	56.8
2.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	107	14.62 (14.99)	45.9	36.2
3.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	72	14.55 (14.99)	49.6	39.7
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	101	14.92 (14.99)	50	42.1
5.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	85	11.52 (11.61)	69	40
6.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	169	11.53 (11.61)	55	45
7.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅	62	14.06 (14.19)	32	27
8.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	99	15.16 (15.20)	65.9	56
9.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	75	15.35 (15.20)	70.1	61
10.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	117	15.18 (15.20)	61	52.6

General method for the preparation of 2-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one-4-yl)-2-(2'-mercapto-3'-aryl-4'-thiazolidone-5'-ylidene)ethane: A solution of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) and 2-mercapto-3-aryl thiazolidone (0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was added dropwise to 40% NaOH (15 ml) and allowed to stand overnight. It was then refluxed for 1 hr on a water bath. Excess of the solvent was removed and the resulting solution was acidified with dil. acetic acid. An yellow solid mass separated which was filtered, washed with water and finally crystallised from ethanol.

Procedure for the synthesis of S-ether product of 2-pyrazolin-5-thione and phenacyl bromide: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (1.9 g) and phenacyl bromide (1.9 g) were taken in ethanol (10 ml) followed by fused sodium acetate (3 g) and was refluxed for 2 hr on a water bath. Excess ethanol was evaporated and cooled and water added. The brown compound thus isolated was then dissolved in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. It was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hr and filtered. The filtrate and the residue were collected separately. The filtrate was acidified with dil. HCl when no product was obtained. The residue was repeatedly washed with water and dried. It was then recrystallised from ethanol. A cream coloured product was obtained, m.p. 49°, yield 60%.

The compound is insoluble in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and does not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	m.p. °C	%S Found (Calcd.)	%inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	47	10.54 (10.38)	70	48

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Flavonoids and other Constituents of

Indigofera hetrantha

ANILA THUSOO, NANCY RAINA

and

SHAKTI RAIS AHMED

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College,
Hazratbal, Srinagar, J & K-190 006

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THE plant *Indigofera hetrantha* (wild) belonging to Leguminosae was collected from Gulmarg, Kashmir in June and was identified in the herbarium of the Botany Department, Kashmir University. The sister species of *Indigofera hetrantha* were found to contain toxic nitro compounds^{1,2} of insecticidal activity³. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate this plant for its chemical composition.

Experimental

The dried plant material (12 kg) was extracted by percolation with ethanol. After removal of the

solvent *in vacuo* at 40° the residue (100 g) was partitioned between 2% aq. citric acid and ether to give a basic and a non-basic fraction. The non-basic fraction was fractionated by standard methods into neutral (20 g), acidic (15 g) and phenolic (6 g) fractions.

The phenolic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh). Elution with CHCl_3 , CHCl_3 -MeOH afforded IH_4 , IH_5 and IH_6 which were purified by re-column chromatography and preparative paper chromatography (Whatman No. 3, 15% HOAc).

The acidic fraction on chromatography over silica gel using C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (1:3) as the eluent gave IH_7 which was purified by recrystallization.

The neutral fraction on chromatography over silica gel using light petrol, petrol- C_6H_6 , C_6H_6 as the eluents afforded IH_1 , IH_2 and IH_3 .

Refrigeration of acidic solution of the basic fraction gave an alkaloidal precipitate (300 mg). The tlc examination of this fraction revealed the presence of several compounds but could not be worked further because of the small amount.

Results

IH_4 : Yellow needles, m.p. 347-8°, M^+ , 270 agreed with elemental analysis of $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$. The compound was identified as apigenin⁴ by uv, ir, nmr, m.m.p. The structure was further confirmed by its conversion to tri-acetate, m.p. 186°.

IH_5 : Yellow needles crystallized from EtOH, m.p. 261°, M^+ , 284 agreed with elemental analysis of $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$. The compound was identified as acacetin^{5,6} by co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir. Acetylation with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{py}$ gave a di-acetate, m.p. 203-5° further confirming its structure.

IH_6 : Yellow needles, m.p. 234-6°, M^+ , 464. The compound was isolated by preparative paper chromatography and gave an olive-green colouration with FeCl_3 . It was identified as isoquercitrin⁷ by uv, ir, nmr and m.m.p. On acid hydrolysis it gave quercitrin⁸, m.p. 313-16° and glucose confirming its structure.

IH_7 : It was identified as ursolic acid¹⁰ (150 mg), m.p. 242-4°. Its ir in KBr pellet showed the following absorption bands: ν_{max} 3450, 2950, 2890, 1685, 1450, 1030 and 990 cm^{-1} . MS: M^+ , 456. Treatment with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{py}$ gave O-acetyl ursolic acid, m.p. 268-270°. Direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p, ir) with an authentic sample confirmed the identity.

IH_1 and IH_2 could not be processed further due to their small amounts.

IH_3 : A white crystalline solid, m.p. 135-6°, was found to be β -sitosterol⁹ by co-tlc and m.m.p.

This appears to be the first record of the isolation of these compounds from this species.